

Utilization and Satisfaction of Dominican Learning Resource Center Resources and Services

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Abstract

This study was conducted to determine the utilization and satisfaction of the resources and services of Dominican Learning Resource Center - Higher Education Department at St. Dominic College of Asia. In this study, a descriptive survey research design was employed with questionnaire as a data collection instrument. A total of six hundred sixty-one (661) respondents participated in this research, but six hundred eleven (611) copies were completed and retrieved. The findings showed that majority of the respondents visited the library and used a computer for online research. It was discovered that respondents were satisfied with all the library resources and services, apart from printing services that are rated neutral. It was also revealed that the users are concerned with the addition of newly updated books, the speed increase of the Internet connection, and the reduction of the printing fees. The researchers recommended provisions for new book collections to ensure in keeping up-to-date information inside and outside the library; printing services to satisfy the users for the convenience; and upgrading the speed of the Internet access for more information toward academic research; in addition to enhancement on the use and facilitation of Online Public Access Catalog (OPAC) and other technologies like computers and tablets for proper training in e-resources. The results of the survey will be useful and beneficial to maintain the library's impact on resources and services for all stakeholders.

Keywords: User satisfaction. Services. Library Resources. Utilization. Satisfaction.

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Introduction

The Library is a place of knowledge and an intellectual reservoir of a college or university. It provides reliable information and preserves recorded knowledge of humankind, which caters to the academic, research, and recreational needs of the stakeholders in the campus. Students, faculty members and staff visit the library to keep abreast accurate, relevant, adequate, and updated information in resources and services for effective and efficient teaching and learning purposes. Thangapandy (2014) states that, new knowledge in every field is emerging throughout the world and that providing efficient information services to the user communities is difficult due to the manner in which the information is managed to enable users to fulfill their requirements.

Academic librarians are facing a variety of challenges and obstacles that are necessary to be solved gradually such as the growing population of enrolled students and appointed faculty members and staffs, the lack of staffs and resources, shortfall of funding resources and services and the library itself, and the addition of tasks given to most, if not all of the members. Fowler (2016) emphasized that the library must guide the community to know into the wider world, based on the parents' public research university (or institution), but also the community-at-large, by the library's involvement in community interaction.

The utilization of reliable resources and services is salient for the users who visit the library. Buhari (2016) posited that the library's information systems have a significant impact on day-to-day operations, and they have the potential to improve their quality and efficacy. Library users are allowed to utilize available resources and services that will help them to satisfy their needs and abilities.

Utilization is one of the factors involved in providing the good quality of services and resources. Ogu and Edam-Agbor (2018) posited that effective utilization of these resources and services is a function of the library use competences exhibited by library users. The use of the library benefits the users, specifically students and faculty members, to support teaching, research, and learning, as well as doing extracurricular activities.

The Dominican Learning Resource Center in the Higher Education Department provides different services that can easily be used and accessed by the students, faculty members, and the staff. The Online Public Access Catalog (OPAC), together with the Internet, computer, and tablet services, help the users find and search relevant collection and information from various sources online.

On the other hand, in-person research assistance and Dominican Online Reference Assistance (DORA) provide the library users with direction to library materials and advices on library collections and services. Referral services help the users to conduct a research outside the libraries and information centers, while library orientations give information on what to do and observe in the library.

Other services such as borrowing, and printing services allow the users to bring resources at home for a limited time period and to print documents needed for various purposes.

User assessments are essential and beneficial to evaluate the satisfaction of library resources and services depending how successful it demands the quality upon the users. This also contributes providing the resources and services needed to ensure how these are effective and efficient in terms of access and development. Onanuga et al. (2017) remarked that the role of library is important in achieving the goals of the parent institution, but their continued relevance is contingent on how well and adequate their programs meet the needs of their customers. Oloteo and Mabesa (2013) noted that librarians should create library marketing strategies along with its program scheme to cater to the satisfaction of library customers.

Libraries are meant to assess how the quality and expectations greatly affect whether the level of satisfaction provided by the users are effective and efficient. The satisfaction of users influences the library in giving the available resources and services to be used in the library. Hussien and Mokhtar (2018) suggested that the librarians should demonstrate their important roles in providing information to the students by giving satisfied response time with high quality information. As for the academic libraries, all the responses regarding with the resources and services are taken into consideration. Problems faced by the users should be resolved if these will make more sufficient and adequate to serve with excellent quality and satisfaction in the library. When students are satisfied with the services, they would be more likely to patronize and advertise (Joshua, 2014).

This study is undertaken to assess the utilization and satisfaction of users of the library resources and services, guided by these objectives: (a) To assess the purpose of users' visit at the library; (b) To determine whether users are satisfied with the library resources and services; and (c) To identify the concerns to be improved in the library.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design to assess the level of satisfaction of the users at the Dominican Learning Resource Center - Higher Education Department. The researchers prepared a survey evaluation questionnaire form which contained a checklist highlighting the purposes of the library usage. 5-point Likert scale (5 – strongly agree, 4 – agree, 3 – neutral, 2 – disagree, 1 – strongly disagree) was utilized to access the library resources and services of DLRC with a comment box for suggestions to improve the library services.

The respondents of this study consisted of six hundred thirty-eight (638) enrolled students, fourteen (14) faculty members, four (4) support staffs, and five (5) department heads of St. Dominic College of Asia during the Second Semester of the Academic Year 2017-2018. Of the six hundred sixty-one (661) questionnaires administered to the library users, only six hundred eleven (611) or 92.44% were completed and returned. The data gathered was tabulated and analyzed using frequency, percentage distribution, and weighted mean.

Results and Discussion

It is shown in Table 1 that two hundred twenty-seven (227) or 37.15% of the users were from Senior High School (SHS), while one hundred forty-six (146) or 23.90% were from the School of Business and Computer Studies (SBCS). One hundred eight (108) or 17.67% of the respondents were from the School of Health Science Professions (SHSP), while sixty-five (65) or 10.64% were from the School of Arts, Sciences, and Education (SASE). In like manner, sixty (60) or 9.82% of the participants come from the School of International Hospitality and Tourism Management (SIHTM), while five (5) or 0.82% come from the Department of Administrative Services and Support (DASS); two from the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) department, one from the Community Outreach Extension Office (COEO), one from the Research Development Office (RDO), and one from the said department office. This shows that majority of the respondents are from the SHS.

Table 1 Departments of respondents (n=611)

No.	Department	Frequency	Percentage
1	SHS	227	37.15%
2	SBCS	148	23.90%
3	SHSP	108	17.67%
4	SASE	65	10.64%
5	SIHTM	60	9.82%
6	DASS	5	0.82%

Table 2 illustrates the users' purposes for library visit. The results revealed that four hundred eleven (411) or 67.27% of the users used a computer for online research. This was followed by three hundred fifty-four (354) or 57.94% who used or borrowed books; three hundred fifty (350) or 57.28% responded having a quiet and comfortable place to study; three hundred seven (307) or 50.25% did research work on their own; and eighty-four (84) or 13.75% use reserve materials for a class. Twenty-one (21) or 3.44% of the participants specified other reasons for visiting the library: fourteen (14) said that they use to relax and meditate, sleep, and use Wi-Fi services; four (4) answered for printing purposes; two (2) responded doing activities at the library, meeting, and class; and one (1) answered for charging of laptop.

Therefore, of all the major services at DLRC, using a computer for online research is utilized by the majority of the respondents. With this development, Yebowaah (2017) states as many users including graduate students who resorted to the use of traditional internet sources for their academic work. Although, users are conveniently using both the library and internet resources in providing relevant information sources for different purposes.

Table 2 Purpose of library visit (n=611)

No.	Purpose	Frequency	Percentage
1	Use a computer for online research	411	67.27%
2	Use or borrow book(s)	354	57.94%
3	Have a quiet, comfortable place to study	350	57.28%
4	Do research work on my own	307	50.25%
5	Use reserve materials for a class	84	13.75%
6	Others	21	3.44%
	Charge laptop	1	
	Do activities at the library, meeting, and class	2	
	Print documents	4	
	Relax and meditate; sleep; use Wi-Fi	14	

As illustrated in Table 3 which reveals the users' satisfaction rating of the library and its resources, based on the results, the respondents agreed that the staff members of the library are helpful and knowledgeable and that the library is a pleasant and comfortable place for studying, as shown by the ratings of 4.12 and 4.07, respectively. The respondents also agreed that the library has books and journals they are looking for and that the library collections are updated, as shown by the ratings of 3.79, 3.62, and 3.60, respectively. It is implied that most of the users agreed with satisfaction of the library services and its resources.

Mairaj and Naseer (2013) said that when it comes to determining a person's perspective, attitude is always important for most of the library personnel and that they should be humble, well-behaved, and helpful. In addition, libraries must not only have a substantial collection of books, periodicals, journals, and other print materials, but they must also subscribe to electronic resources, purchase modern technology, create solid infrastructure, allocate adequate space, recruit competent personnel, and enhance standards (Sheikh, 2014). Therefore, it helps the library to enhance customer demands and expectations and makes the users more convenient in improving the resources to ensure that they are useful in academic and social purposes.

Table 3 Satisfaction rating of the library and its resources

No.	Statement	Rating	Interpretation
1	Staff members of the library are helpful and knowledgeable.	4.12	Agree
2	The library is a pleasant place for studying.	4.07	Agree
3	The library has the books I am looking for.	3.79	Agree
4	The library has the journals I am looking for.	3.62	Agree
5	The library collections are updated.	3.60	Agree

Legend: 4.5 – 5.0 (Strongly Agree); 3.5 – 4.49 (Agree); 2.5 – 3.49 (Neutral); 1.5 – 2.49 (Disagree); 1.0 – 1.49 (Strongly Disagree)

As presented in Table 4 which shows the users' satisfaction rating of the library services, the findings revealed that the users were satisfied of the Online Public Access Catalog (OPAC) and borrowing services, as shown by the mean ratings of 3.79 and 4.00, respectively. Moreover, the users also agreed with the satisfaction of other services such as Internet services (M=3.82), computer and tablet services (M=3.83), referral services (M=3.72), library orientation (M=3.77), in-person research assistance (M=3.76), and online reference assistance (DORA) [M=3.74]. However, the respondents expressed with neutrality of the printing services, with the mean rating of 3.47. It implies that most of the users are satisfied with the overall services, excluding the printing services.

It implies that most of the users are satisfied with the overall services, excluding the printing services. The role of academic libraries in the growth of academic libraries is critical, especially in terms of professional development and resource exchange (Fresnido and Yap, 2014). It shows that the services lie on the users as a way to ensure that their needs and goals are met when these are used effectively.

Table 4 Satisfaction rating of the library services

No.	Library services	Rating	Interpretation
1	OPAC	3.79	Agree
2	Borrowing services	4.00	Agree
3	Printing services	3.47	Neutral
4	Internet services	3.82	Agree
5	Computer and tablet services	3.83	Agree
6	Referral services	3.72	Agree
7	Library orientation	3.77	Agree
8	In-person research assistance	3.76	Agree
9	Online reference assistance (DORA)	3.74	Agree

Legend: 4.5 – 5.0 (Strongly Agree); 3.5 – 4.49 (Agree); 2.5 – 3.49 (Neutral); 1.5 – 2.49 (Disagree); 1.0 – 1.49 (Strongly Disagree)

As expressed in Table 5 that pertains to the concerns regarding the improvement of library resources and services, thirty-three (33) comments were provided by the users that the library needs to be improved. Based on the findings, the top three major concerns were suggested by the respondents: seventy-nine (79) users suggested updating and adding more books; fifty-two (52) asked to improve the speed of Wi-Fi and Internet connections; and forty-six (46) for reduction of printing fee.

These concerns indicated that although the DLRC-HED users were satisfied with the library resources and services, they realized that the following concerns on the library mentioned on the table were considered. Namugera (2014) noted that library services should be strongly promoted and marketed using a variety of approaches to increase customer awareness and usage of all library services. It implies that more effort should be done in order to enhance such services needed for the betterment and convenience of the users.

Table 5 Concerns on the library resources and services

Concerns	Frequency	Rank
Update and add more books.	79	1
Improve the speed of Wi-Fi and Internet connection.	52	2
Lessen the amount of printing fee.	46	3
Expand the space of the library for comfort.	31	4
Add more computers.	23	5
There must be proper ventilation in the library.	19	6
Have more updated journals and magazines.	17	7
Maintain the stability of all computers, mouse, and keyboards.	15	8
Printing services should be available every day.	13	9
Improve the study environment of the library.	11	10.5
Improve facilities and services for convenience and conducive to learning.	11	10.5
Implement strict rules of observance in the library (e.g. no noise policy).	10	12
Unblock sites that are necessary for research.	9	13
Lessen or remove the book penalty for both faculty and students.	7	14.5
Implement the monitoring system in the computer section.	7	14.5
Have more research materials.	6	16.5
Install applications in all computers (e.g. Anti-virus, Multimedia).	6	16.5
Extend longer days of borrowing for both faculty and students.	5	18.5
Staffs should exert more effort and be more approachable and helpful.	5	18.5
Increase the socket outlets for charging.	4	21.5
Maintain the orderliness of the library.	4	21.5
Improve the arrangement of books.	4	21.5
Provide sleeping areas or relax stations for students.	4	21.5
Borrow more than two books.	3	26
Provide more online databases.	3	26
Improve the printing services.	3	26
Ambiance must be improved, especially the lightings.	3	26
Other entrances of the library should be open for students.	3	26
Create a coffee lounge inside the library.	2	31
Extend the library hours for studying or answering homework.	2	31
Provide comfortable seats, couches, and tables.	2	31
Keep the floor clean and dry.	2	31
Separate the area of computer section.	2	31

Conclusion and Recommendations

The Dominican Learning Resource Center – Higher Education Department has been extensively used by the stakeholders of St. Dominic College of Asia in the academic pursuits impacting in the vision and mission of this institution of which to become the most dynamic library in Asia and to provide equitable access to information by continuously acquiring world-class library resources in support of quality education, training, research, and community service of the College.

Based on the findings, a better DLRC will evolve through: provision for new book collections to ensure in keeping up-to-date information inside and outside the library; reliable and stable provision for printing services in the library in order to satisfy the users such that the said services must have a printing queue for users who print documents and staffs must reduce a printing fee from five pesos to three pesos for the convenience; provision for upgrading the speed of the Internet access which provides access to more information toward academic research; an enhancement on the use and facilitation of OPAC and other information and communication technologies (ICTs) like computers and tablets for proper training in e-library resources. Finally, the library should design a special program for the researchers that will help the users to assist in searching for the appropriate library collections and services as a contribution to the library's impact.

References

- Buhari, G. I. (2016). Library information resources and services utilization as correlates of creativity of senior administrative staff of Polytechnics in South West, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice* (e-journal), 1400. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/1400>
- Fowler, G. (2016). *The essence of the library at a public research university as seen through key constituents' lived experiences* (Doctoral dissertation). Old Dominion University, Norfolk, Virginia.
- Fresnido, A. M. B., & Yap, J. M. (2014). Academic library consortia in the Philippines: Hanging in the balance. *Library Management*, 35(1/2), 15-36. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LM-04-2013-0028>
- Hussien, F. R. M., & Mokhtar, W. N. H. W. (2018). The effectiveness of reference services and users' satisfaction in the academic library. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 7(3), 327-337. <http://dx.doi.org/10.6007/IJARPED/v7-i3/4370>
- Joshua, D. (2014). Users' assessment of e-resources at the university library of the University of the Philippines, Diliman. *Journal of Philippine Librarianship*, 34, 1-13.
- Mairaj, M. J., & Naseer, M. M. (2013). Library services and user satisfaction in developing countries: A case study. *Health Information and Libraries Journal*, 30(4), 318-326. <https://doi.org/10.1111/hir.12038>
- Namugera, L. (2014). Users' awareness, perceptions and usage of Makerere library services in the main and selected branch libraries. *Qualitative and Quantitative Methods in Libraries*, 3, 741-758.

- Ogu, J. O. and Edam-Agbor, I. B. (2018). Library use instruction and the pattern of utilization of library services by undergraduates in the University of Calabar, Nigeria. *Global Educational of Journal Research*, 17, 87-95.
- Oloteo, R. B., & Mabesa, H. A. Jr. (2013). Library services and customer satisfaction in state universities and colleges in the Bicol region. *Journal of Philippine Librarianship*, 33(1), 1-14.
- Onanuga, A. O., Ilori, O. O., Pelemo, G. D. & Ogunwande, O. O. (2017). Library services utilization and satisfaction by undergraduate students: A case study of Osun State University Main Library. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 22(5), 83-88.
- Sheikh, A. (2014). Quality of CIIT library services and users' satisfaction: A survey of students, faculty and staff members. *Libri*, 64(1), 49-60.
<https://doi.org/10.1515/libri-2014-0005>
- Thangapandy, M. (2014). Utilization of library resources by the students of G D institutions: A case study. *Paripex – Indian Journal of Research*, 3(7), 1-4.
- Yebowaah, F.A. (2017). Comparative study of library and internet use as a source of information by graduate students of the University for Development Studies, Ghana. *Library Philosophy and Practice* (e-journal), 1606.
<http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/1606>